

Total Bilirubin Assay Kit Instruction

(A019-1 Total Bilirubin kit, TBIL Chemical Oxidase Method)

【Application】

This kit was used for quantitative determination of total bilirubin in serum (blood plasma). Serum (blood plasma) total bilirubin is common in hepatitis, extrahepatic biliary tract obstruction, hemolytic disease and so on.

【Principle】

Total bilirubin was oxidized by sodium nitrite in the presence of surfactant Triton X-100. The decrease in absorbance at 405nm is proportional to its concentration.

【Composition: 96T】

Reagent	Specifications	Composition	Concentration
Reagent 1	24ml×1 bottle	Tris-Hcl	50×10^{-3} mol/L
		Triton X-100	10ml/L
Reagent 2	6ml×1 bottle	PBS	10×10^{-3} mol/L
		Nitrite	80×10^{-3} mol/L

【Storage Conditions and Validity period】

The reagents can stable for 1 year at 2~8°C. Transport in summer is refrigerated, not frozen. It can be kept for 1 month at 2~8°C after open.

【Sample Request】

Serum or blood plasma. The blood should be separated in time to avoid hemolysis. And keep it avoid light

【Inspection Methods】

1、 Operation

	Blank	Assay
ddH ₂ O (μl)	8	
Sample (μl)		8
Reagent 1 (μl)	240	240
Mix thoroughly and incubate at 37°C for 3~5 indeterminate A0 at 405nm		
Reagent 2 (μl)	60	60
Mix thoroughly and incubate at 37°C for 3~5 indeterminate A0 at 405nm $\Delta A = A_0 - A_1$		

Note: Practice multi-channel pipettor operation.

【Formula】

$$\text{T-BIL } (\mu\text{mol/L}) = 887.211 \times (\Delta A_{\text{assay}} - \Delta A_{\text{Blank}}) + 0.5492$$

【Reference Range】

Healthy adults: 3.42-20.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (0.2-1.2 mg/dL)

(It is recommended that each laboratory establish its own reference range.)

【Limitation】

- 1、 The determination of TBIL is only one of the indicators of scientific research, and it is also necessary to make a comprehensive judgment based on the sample body's other experimental items and methods.
- 2、 Interfering substance: NO interference when Hemoglobin \leq 25g/L, VC \leq 30mg/dl, TG \leq 2000mg/dl.

【Performance Index】

Blank absorbance value: $A_{450\text{nm}}$ (10mm) \leq 0.05,

Linear range:3.4 ~ 684 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (a.Linear correlation coefficient $R^2 \geq 0.995$.b.3.4-100 $\mu\text{mol/L}$,
Linear deviation \leq 10.0 $\mu\text{mol/L}$,100-684 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, Linear deviation \leq 10.0%).

Accuracy: Relative deviation \leq 10.0%

Precision: Inter-batch CV $<$ 4.0%,Intra bath CV \leq 6.0%

Sensitivity: when the sample concentration is 90 $\mu\text{mol/L}$,the OD value is not less than 0.04;

【Announcement】

- 1、 The kit is for scientific research use only. If the reagent is accidentally splashed into the skin ,eyes and so on, you must wash with clean water. Accidental ingestion must be treated in the hospital.
- 2、 The standard product is easy to decompose, so we don't provide it in the kit. You can calculate refer to our standard curve or calculation formula.
- 3、 Sample and the reagents dosage can be adjusted according to you need; Different batches of reagents must not be mixed.
- 4、 Precautions should be taken when using and following all laboratory reagent operations.All wastes shall be disposed in accordance with local regulations.

【Standard Curve】

Standard Concentration	0	8.81	11.01	17.62	29.37	44.05	58.73	88.10
A ₀	0.0383	0.0486	0.0489	0.0551	0.0690	0.0911	0.1151	0.1464
A ₁	0.0363	0.0377	0.0354	0.0340	0.0346	0.0406	0.0451	0.0463
ΔA	0.0020	0.0109	0.0135	0.0211	0.0344	0.0505	0.0700	0.1001
ΔA-Δ0	0	0.0089	0.0115	0.0191	0.0324	0.0485	0.0680	0.0981

Determine the ΔOD according to the above scheme with 88.10μmol/ Standard, and made the standard curve according to the ΔOD corresponding to different concentrations.

